

DELAMINATION FATIGUE PROPERTIES OF Z-PINNED CARBON-EPOXY LAMINATE USING METAL OR COMPOSITE RODS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental study into improvements to the mode I (crack opening) and mode II (crack sliding) delamination fatigue properties of carbon fibre-epoxy laminate reinforced through-the-thickness with metal or carbon fibre rods. The z-pins were made of unidirectional carbon fibre composite, copper, stainless steel or titanium. The delamination fatigue properties were measured in cyclic displacement control using the double cantilever beam (DCB) test for mode I and end notch flexure (ENF) test for mode II. Both the metal and carbon z-pins are effective at resisting the initiation and growth of delamination cracks under cyclic mode I and mode II loads, although the fatigue strengthening effect was greater for mode I, irrespective of the z-pin material. The fatigue resistance increases due to the z-pins forming of a large-scale extrinsic bridging zone along the fatigue crack. The influence of the material properties of the z-pins on their fatigue strengthening capacity and fatigue failure mode is determined.

1 INTRODUCTION

Delamination cracking is a long standing problem with laminated composite materials due to the low strength and toughness of the polymer matrix and matrix/fibre interface. Delamination can grow rapidly under low interlaminar fatigue loads, often with the cracks being undetectable via visual inspection [1-3]. A large number of numerical and experimental studies have proven that z-pinning is an effective through-thickness reinforcement method for increasing the modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness of laminated composites [4-10]. Several studies have also reported that z-pinning can increase the delamination fatigue resistance of composites under mode I and II cyclic loading [11-16]. The fracture toughening and fatigue strengthening depends on several parameters, including volume content, diameter and embedded length of the z-pins.

However, research performed to date has focussed almost entirely on composites reinforced with carbon fibre z-pins, and delamination property improvements gained by other pin materials have not been as thoroughly assessed. Cox et al. [17] showed that titanium z-pins are highly effective at

increasing the mode II delamination resistance of composites, and plastically deform in shear at high crack sliding displacements. More recently, Chio and colleagues investigated the improvement to the fatigue resistance of a composite single-lap joint reinforced in the bonded region with thin stainless steel rods [18-19]. Apart from these few studies, the delamination toughness and fatigue properties of composites with metal z-pins have not been thoroughly studied .

This paper presents an experimental investigation into the influence of the z-pin material on the delamination fatigue resistance of z-pinned carbon-epoxy composite. Z-pin materials with different elastic stiffness, yield stress, ultimate stress and fatigue strength properties were used, and these were copper, stainless steel, titanium and carbon fibre pins. The study aims to determine the effect of these different z-pin materials on the delamination fatigue properties and fatigue strengthening mechanism under mode I and II interlaminar cyclic loading.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Z-Pinned Composite Materials

Unpinned and z-pinned composite specimens were manufactured to measure the mode I and mode II delamination fatigue properties. The specimens were made using unidirectional (UD) T700 carbon fibre-epoxy prepreg tape (VTM264 supplied by Advanced Composite Group) stacked in a $[0_6/[90/0]_2]_s$ ply sequence. Uncured samples were reinforced in the through-thickness (orthogonal) direction with unidirectional carbon fibre-bismaleimide (BMI), copper (99.9% purity), titanium (grade 1; 99.5% purity) or stainless steel (316L) pins. The tensile properties of these z-pin materials are given in Table 1.

Material Mechanical Properties (20°C)	Tensile Modulus [GPa]	Yield Stress 0.2% Offset [MPa]	Ultimate Tensile Strength [MPa]	Elongation to Failure [%]	Shear Modulus [MPa]
Cu (99.9% purity)	117	70	222	86	48
Titanium (grade 1; 99.5% purity)	105	309	390	24	45
Stainless Steel (316L)	200	170	485	55 (sheet)	82
Carbon fibre-BMI	140		2300	1.6	

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the z-pin materials used as reinforcement.

The spacing (3.2 mm), diameter (510 μm), volume content (2%), and length (4 mm) of the different z-pins were the same; the only difference was the z-pin material. The carbon z-pins were inserted into the uncured composite using the ultrasonically assisted pinning (UAZ) process, which is fully described in [20]. Metal pins were individually and manually inserted into the uncured composite. Before insertion, the metal z-pins were cleaned and then surface treated with a silane-coupling agent (3-methacryloxypropyl-trimethoxysilane) to promote bonding with the composite during curing.

The z-pinned composite (4 mm thick) was sandwiched between two unpinned unidirectional carbon-epoxy tabs (each 4.5 mm thick) to prevent failure of the specimen arms during fatigue testing, as shown in Figure 1. A control material consisting of the unpinned $[0_6/[90/0]_2]_s$ carbon-epoxy laminate was made to the same specimen dimensions as the z-pinned composites. The unpinned and z-pinned composites were cured and consolidated in an autoclave at 120°C and 620 kPa for one hour. The carbon fibre volume content of the different composites was the same at ~58%.

2.2 Delamination Fatigue Testing

Mode I and mode II fatigue properties were measured by using the double cantilever beam (DCB) test and end notched flexure (ENF) test, respectively. The two testing configurations are shown in

figure 1. The DCB and ENF samples contained respectively a 50 mm and 40 mm long pre-crack at the mid-plane to initiate the delamination fatigue crack. The DCB and ENF samples were cyclically loaded in displacement control at a frequency of 10 Hz and R ratio of 0.1, which is defined as the ratio between the minimum and maximum displacements per load cycle. The samples were fatigued under constant cyclic displacement conditions for allow the delamination to grow by 5-10 mm. From this the fatigue crack growth rate, which is defined as the average crack extension length per load cycle, was measured. The growth of the fatigue crack was monitored and its length measured using a travelling optical microscope located to one-side of the DCB or ENF sample. This process was repeated over a wide range of cyclic intensities (ΔG) values.

The mode I cyclic intensity range (ΔG_I) was calculated from the difference between the maximum and minimum interlaminar strain energy intensity values:

$$\Delta G_I = G_{I(max)} - G_{I(min)} \quad (1)$$

where

$$G_{I(max)} = \frac{3P_{I(max)}\delta_{I(max)}}{2b(a+|\Delta l|)} \quad (2)$$

and

$$G_{I(min)} = \frac{3P_{I(min)}\delta_{I(min)}}{2b(a+|\Delta l|)} \quad (3)$$

$P_{I(max)}$ and $P_{I(min)}$ are the maximum and minimum applied loads and $\delta_{I(max)}$ and $\delta_{I(min)}$ are the maximum and minimum displacements in one fatigue cycle. $|\Delta l|$ is a correction factor which account for rotation effects and vertical displacement at the crack tip. b and a are the specimen width and delamination crack length, respectively.

The mode II fatigue intensity range (ΔG_{II}) was calculated using:

$$\Delta G_{II} = G_{II(max)} - G_{II(min)} \quad (4)$$

where $G_{II(max)}$ and $G_{II(min)}$ are the maximum and minimum mode II strain energy intensity values, and are calculated as:

$$G_{II(max)} = \frac{9a^2 P_{II(max)} \delta_{II(max)}}{2b(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad (5)$$

and

$$G_{II(min)} = \frac{9a^2 P_{II(min)} \delta_{II(min)}}{2b(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad (6)$$

P_{II} is the applied bending force, δ_{II} is the bending displacement, and L is the distance between the loading and support points for the ENF test.

Multiple samples of the unpinning and different types of z-pinned composites were fatigue tested under mode I and II conditions.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Schematic of the mode I DCB test (a) and mode II ENF test (b).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mode I Delamination Fatigue Properties

Paris curves showing plots of the mode I cyclic intensity range (ΔG_I) against the delamination crack growth rate (da/dN) for the unpinned laminate and the composites reinforced with the different z-pin materials are presented in figure 2. There is significant scatter in the Paris curves, and this was caused by the slip (crack advance)-stick (crack arrest) behaviour of the fatigue cracking. The z-pins increased the delamination fatigue resistance of the composite, although the magnitude of fatigue strengthening was dependent on the pin material. The fatigue strengthening effect of the z-pins increased in the order: copper (worse), titanium, stainless steel and then carbon (best) pins. This proves the mode I fatigue strengthening of z-pinned composites is dependent on the material

properties of the z-pins. This discovery adds to research which has already revealed that the mode I fatigue properties are also controlled by the volume content [11-15], diameter [13-15] and length [13, 16] of the pins.

The Paris curves show that the ΔG_I value needed to initiate delamination growth under cyclic mode I loading was improved by z-pinning, irrespective of the z-pin material. It was not possible to precisely determine the ΔG_I initiation values for the different composites due to intrinsically large amount of scatter in the measured crack growth rates. For this reason, the initiation values (ΔG_{Ii}) were taken at the crack growth rate of 1×10^{-6} mm/cycle, which is very close to the threshold ΔG_I when fatigue cracking starts. The ΔG_I initiation values for the unpinned and z-pinned composites are given in Table 2. The table also gives the ΔG_I values for fast (unstable) fatigue crack growth, which occurs at rates above ~ 0.1 -1 mm/cycle. This value was increased considerably by z-pinning, with the carbon z-pin providing a greater fatigue strengthening effect than the metal pins. The gradient of the mode I Paris curves within the log-log linear region (defined by the parameter m_I) are given in Table 2. The m_I value defines the sensitivity of the fatigue crack growth process for a material to changes in ΔG_I . There are differences in the m_I value between the materials, however due to the high amount of scatter (as indicated by the linear correlation coefficient) it is inconclusive whether z-pinning has any significant effect. Also, the m_I values for the z-pinned composites are higher and lower than the unpinned laminate, and no clear correlation exists.

Figure 2: Effect of z-pin material on the mode I Paris curve for the carbon-epoxy composite.

Z-pin	ΔG_{II} [kJ/m ²]	ΔG_{IC} [kJ/m ²]	m_I	Linear correlation coefficient (R)
None	0.16	0.95	7.4	0.82
Copper	0.47 (2.9x)	6.0 (6.4x)	5.7	0.40
Stainless steel	0.92 (5.7x)	12.0 (12.7x)	6.2	0.85
Titanium	0.51 (3.2x)	10.9 (11.5x)	4.5	0.65
Carbon	1.07 (6.7x)	9.6 (10.1x)	7.2	0.47

Table 2: ΔG_I values for the initiation crack growth (ΔG_{II}), fast delamination crack growth (ΔG_{IC}) and Paris curve parameter ' m_I ' for the unpinned and z-pinned composites. The last column gives the linear correlation coefficient for the m_I value. The numbers in brackets give the times improvement of the z-pin composites compared to the unpinned laminate.

The z-pins increased the mode I fatigue resistance by forming a large-scale bridging zone along the delamination crack, irrespective of the pin material. Due to the high stiffness and strength of the z-pins, they resist cyclic crack opening which increases the ΔG to initiate fatigue crack growth, slows the crack growth rate under steady-state fatigue conditions, and raise the ΔG value to cause fast fatigue fracture. The z-pins towards the rear of the bridging zone eventually failed under cyclic loading, which then allowed the fatigue crack to advance. However, the fatigue failure mechanism of the z-pins was dependent on their material properties. The metal z-pins failed at or very close to the delamination crack plane by tensile fatigue cracking. For example, Figure 3 shows a copper z-pin on the delamination surface which has failed by the growth of a single fatigue crack, which initiated at the pin surface (most likely a pre-existing flaw). The fracture surfaces of the metal z-pins showed the beach mark striations characteristic of ductile fatigue crack growth. The spacing between the beach marks increased with the mode I ΔG value applied to the composites reinforced with metal z-pins. This is indicative of accelerated fatigue crack growth in the z-pins, which then caused the delamination fatigue crack growth rate of the z-pinned composites to increase with ΔG . The fatigue failure process of the carbon z-pins was different, and involved interfacial debonding following by complete pull-out, as shown in Figure 4. The carbon z-pins themselves were not damaged by the fatigue loading, and presumably this is because unidirectional carbon fibre composite (from which these pins were made) have much higher tensile fatigue resistance than commercially pure copper, titanium (Grade 1) or stainless steel. The resistance of the carbon z-pins to fatigue-induced tensile fracture is a key factor towards its high fatigue strengthening efficiency. Instead, these pins fail by pull-out which generates high cyclic traction loads as they slid back and forth against the composite [12], and this is a highly effective fatigue strengthening mechanism for z-pinned composites [13].

Figure 3: Mode I fatigue failure of a metal (copper) z-pin. The fatigue-induced striations on the fracture surface of the z-pin are shown in (b).

Figure 4: Mode I fatigue failure of a carbon z-pin. (a) and (b) show respectively the pull-out pin and the hole this created.

3.2 Mode II Delamination Fatigue Properties

Z-pinning was also effective at increasing the mode II delamination fatigue resistance of the composites. Figure 5 presents Paris curves showing the effect of the mode II cyclic intensity (ΔG_{II}) on the crack growth rate for the unpinned laminate and the composites reinforced with different types of z-pin. The mode II fatigue parameters are given in table 3. Similar to mode I, scatter in the mode II delamination growth rates was caused by stick-slip of the fatigue crack. Within the bounds of experimental scatter in the crack growth rates, there was no significant different between the mode II delamination fatigue resistance of the composites reinforced with copper, titanium or stainless z-pins,

unlike the mode I fatigue properties which were dependent on the type of metal. The increase to the mode II delamination fatigue properties due to z-pinning was less pronounced than for mode I, particularly at intermediate cyclic intensity values (ΔG_{II} between ~ 0.3 and 1.0 kJ/m^2) when there was only a marginal improvement. Z-pins were more effective at increasing the mode II fatigue resistance at relatively low and high cyclic intensity values when the crack growth rate was slow and fast, respectively. The ΔG_{III} value to initiate fatigue cracking was increased by about 5 times with the metal z-pins and more than ten times with the carbon z-pins. Z-pinning was also effective at mode II fatigue strengthening at high cyclic intensity values when the crack growth rate was fast (above $0.1\text{-}1 \text{ mm/cycle}$), particularly the carbon pin. The results also show that the sensitivity of the delamination fatigue properties (defined by the parameter m_{II}) to the z-pin material was not significant.

Figure 5: Effect of z-pin material on the mode II Paris curve for the carbon-epoxy composite.

Z-Pin	$\Delta G_{III} [\text{kJ/m}^2]$	$\Delta G_{IIc} [\text{kJ/m}^2]$	m_{II}	Linear correlation coefficient (R)
None	0.03	1.05	2.4	0.87
Copper	0.19 (6.8x)	4.4 (4.2x)	5.0	0.94
Stainless steel	0.20 (7.1x)	6.1 (5.8x)	4.8	0.92
Titanium	0.19 (6.8x)	5.0 (4.8x)	4.7	0.93
Carbon	0.52 (17.6x)	10.6 (10.1x)	3.6	0.91

Table 3: ΔG_{II} values for the initiation crack growth (ΔG_{III}), fast delamination crack growth (ΔG_{IIc}) and Paris curve parameter ' m_{II} ' for the unpinned and z-pinned composites. The last column gives the linear correlation coefficient for the m_{II} value. The numbers in brackets give the times improvement of the z-pin composites compared to the unpinned laminate.

The mode II fatigue properties were improved by the z-pins creating a large-scale bridging zone along the delamination crack. Figure 6 shows examples of a metal and carbon z-pin bridging a mode

II fatigue crack, and figure 7 shows these pins on the crack surfaces after failure. There were substantial difference in the deformation and failure modes of the ductile metal and brittle carbon z-pins. The metal z-pins plastically deformed in a region localised to the delamination crack plane. The shear strain deformation increased with the amount of crack sliding displacement applied in a single load cyclic. The metal z-pins would have cyclically strain hardened under repeated loading, causing their yield stress to increase. However, the cyclic strains were too low to cause the metal z-pins to completely fail, unlike mode I. The carbon z-pins bridging the mode II fatigue crack failed progressively by shear rupture close to the delamination. The carbon z-pins failed by longitudinal splitting cracking between the fibres and transverse shear rupture of the individual fibres until eventually the entire pin failed at the delamination crack plane. Despite these differences in the fatigue failure processes of the metal and carbon z-pins, this did not cause significant differences in their mode II fatigue strengthening efficiency except at low and high ΔG_{II} values when the carbon pins were superior.

Figure 6: Photographs showing the shear deformation of a stainless steel z-pin (a) and a shear fracture of a carbon z-pin (b) bridging a mode II fatigue crack.

Figure 7: Fatigue failure mechanism of stainless steel z-pins (a) and carbon fibre z-pin (b) under mode II loading.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Previous studies have shown that the delamination fatigue resistance of z-pinned composites is dependent on the volume content, diameter and length of the z-pins [5-17]. This study has proven that another important parameter controlling the delamination fatigue properties is the material used for the z-pins. The improvement to the mode I fatigue properties was strongly dependent on the z-pin material, which increased in the order of their tensile strength and fatigue resistance (copper (worse), titanium, stainless steel, carbon (best)). The z-pins increased the mode I fatigue resistance by generating a large-scale bridging zone along the delamination. The metal z-pins eventually failed by cyclic tensile fatigue cracking whereas the carbon z-pin, which have higher fatigue strength, failed by interfacial debonding and pull-out. The higher stiffness, strength and fatigue life of the carbon z-pin combined with the high traction load generated during pull-out accounts for its superior fatigue strengthening effect.

The mode II fatigue properties of the composite were also improved by z-pinning, although the magnitude of the fatigue strengthening effect was less than for mode I. The mode II fatigue resistance was increased by the metal and carbon z-pins forming a large-scale bridging zone along the fatigue crack. The metal z-pins plastically deformed close to the delamination crack plane by localised cyclic shear flow, but did not fail. The carbon z-pin also permanently deformed close to the crack plane, although it eventually fractured. Despite these differences in the fatigue responses between the metal and carbon z-pins, this did not change significantly their capacity to increase the mode II delamination failure resistance (except at very low and high ΔG_{II} values when the carbon z-pins were better).

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